

Q1: What RE challenges do you face in your current processes?

Q2: Which categories of RE challenges are most recurrent?

1. Minimal documentation -
2. Customer unavailability -
3. Inappropriate architecture in relation to the requirements -
4. Budget and time estimation -
5. Neglecting non-functional requirements-
6. Customer inability and agreement -
7. Requirements change and its evaluation -

Q3: What was/were your previous approach(es) to address these challenges?

Q4: What motivated you to consider LLMs as an option to address these challenges and/or improve your current processes?

Q5: What do you know about large language models (LLMs)?

Q6 How do you plan to conduct the quality evaluation of the outputs (generated RE artefacts) of the LLMs?

Q7: What do you plan to improve by using these LLM based techniques in your RE processes?

Q8: How do you plan to measure the improvement (if any) in your processes?

Q9: What is the most important characteristic you look for in these LLM based techniques? User friendliness or quality of the output or ease of integration into existing processes?

Q10: There is a risk that the RE artefacts generated using LLMs might be similar (in some ways) to RE artefacts of other organisations that use LLMs in a similar way to yours. Would that be an issue? If yes, how?

Q11: What are the ethical and legal aspects of LLMs being incorporated into your practices that you are worried about? How do you plan address these ethical and legal aspects?

Q12: What do you understand by the term "Prompt Engineering?"

Q13: How much do you know about prompt engineering?

1. No Idea -
2. Heard about it but lack any technical understanding -
3. Have a theoretical understanding of the concept and know some prompt engineering techniques -
4. I know a lot of prompt engineering techniques and patterns and I regularly implement them whenever I'm using an LLM -

Q14: Do you have strategy in mind for the choice of prompt engineering techniques you want to use to interact with the LLMs during the workshop?

